

PRINCIPLES FOR STANDARDIZATION OF TERMS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR TRANSLATING TOURISM TERMS INTO ENGLISH

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada turistlar va mahalliy aholi o'rtasida samarali muloqot qilish uchun turizm atamalarini ishonchli tarjima qilish muhimligi muhokama qilinadi. U turizm terminologiyasini ingliz tiliga tarjima qilishni standartlashtirish bo'yicha yo'riqnomalarni ishlab chiqish jarayonini taqdim etadi hamda turizm va madaniy terminologiyaning maqbulligini o'rganishga asoslangan tavsiyalarni taqdim etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: turistik atamalar, tarjima, aloqa, uslubiy tavsiyalar, madaniy terminologiya.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается важность достоверного перевода туристических терминов для эффективной коммуникации между туристами и местными жителями. В нем представлен процесс разработки руководящих принципов по стандартизации перевода туристической терминологии на английский язык и представлены рекомендации, основанные на исследованиях приемлемости туристической и культурной терминологии.

Ключевые слова: туристические термины, перевод, коммуникация, методические рекомендации, культурологическая терминология.

Abstract. The article discusses the importance of reliable translation of tourism terms for effective communication between tourists and local residents. It presents the process of developing guidelines for standardizing the translation of tourism terminology into English, and provides recommendations based on research into the acceptability of tourism and cultural terminology.

Keywords: tourism terms, translation, communication, guidelines, cultural terminology.

In the modern world, tourism plays an important role in the economic development of many countries, including the Republic of Korea. Republic of Korea attracts a significant number of tourists from different countries, which requires ensuring communication efficiency and understanding of tourism terms in different

languages. Reliable translation of tourism terms is essential for effective communication between tourists and local residents, and also influences the creation of conditions that are favorable and culturally adapted for a comfortable stay for tourists. The article describes the process of developing guidelines for standardizing the translation of tourism terminology into English, and presents final recommendations based on research into the acceptability of tourism and cultural terminology. Choi Hee Seop's study suggests the following four things:

1. Collaboration with cultural property experts: When translating cultural property, translators should collaborate with cultural property experts. This will allow us to achieve a more accurate and adequate translation, taking into account the characteristics and nuances of each culture.

2. Review of the draft by native English speakers: Before the translation is published, the draft must be reviewed by native English speakers. Managers should review the draft, correct grammatical errors, and suggest vocabulary that is understandable to the average English speaker.

3. Development of a system for studying theories of translation of cultural property: it is recommended to develop a system for studying theories of translation of cultural property in universities and other educational institutions. This will make it possible to prepare specialists with the necessary knowledge and skills for high-quality translation of cultural terms.

4. Hiring competent translators and training them: Organizations working in the field of tourism and culture should hire competent translators and oblige them to constantly improve their skills in the field of cultural translation. These recommendations will help improve the process of translating cultural terms and ensure a more accurate and adequate perception of cultural information in English.

Principles of standardization when translating into English. The Guide to Translating Tourism Terms into English is based on primary and secondary in-depth research that included collecting specific opinions from local people in 3 languages to improve, adjust and localize the terms.

The following principles were taken into account when developing the guide:

1. Taking into account the type and nature of the term: when translating each term, its type and characteristics are taken into account. The term must convey a fairly accurate meaning and maintain the uniqueness of the Korean tourism term.

2. Consistency: When translating similar terms or elements representing the same concept, Term ensures maximum consistency in the choice of translation.

The guide has been developed based on in-depth research and information collected. The study proposed multiple translations for 20 titles to test the perceptions of native English speakers and to gather practical alternatives and opinions. These

data served as the basis for developing preliminary translation guidelines for each type of tourism term, including attractions, lifestyle information, and experiences.

Name of tourist destinations. Guidelines for translating unique and communicative place names vary depending on the type: natural places, man-made places, and cultural heritage.

1. *Natural geographical names:* For mountains, rivers, lakes, passes and other natural geographical features, it is recommended to use the romanization of Korean names and represent the semantic part of the last element with a capital letter. For example, “Hangang River” remains unchanged, “Hallasan Mountain” and “Seopjikoji Cape” become “Hallasan Mountain”. However, in the case of space restrictions such as road signs and maps, names may be omitted or abbreviated. For example, Seomjingang River can be translated as “Seomjingang River” or “Seomjingang Riv”.

2. *Artificial Place Names:* For artificial place names such as buildings, ports and parks, it is recommended to use Roman letters for all elements and represent the semantic part of the last element. For example, “Gwangjang Market” denotes the entire “Plaza” element, while “Dodong Yak Water Park” and “Gwangyang Maehwa Village” become “Dodong Mineral Spring Park” and “Gwangyang Plum Flower Village”. If all elements include natural place names, follow the guidelines for translating natural place names, but abbreviations are allowed to avoid too long translations. For piers and temples, all names in Korean are also romanized and the semantic part of the last element is added. For example, 경주보 (Gyeongju Bo) becomes “Gyeongju Bridge”, and 산방굴사 (Sanbanggulsa) is proposed to be translated as “Sanbanggulsa Grotto”.

3. *Cultural Heritage:* Cultural heritage names should be designated in accordance with the standards for English cultural heritage designation. For example, “Sungnyemun” is translated as “Sungnyemun Gate”, and “Dabotap” becomes “Dabotap Pagoda”. If there is an official English name used by the competent authority or company, it is recommended that you stick to that name. For example, if the official name for “Plaza Hotel” is “Plaza”, then that name should be used. These guidelines will help ensure accurate and informative translation of place names, taking into account the context and priority of conveying information about places.

Lifestyle information. For terms related to lifestyle information, such as housing, transport, shops and alleys, recommendations have been developed with a priority of accurately conveying facts that are practically necessary for users.

1. *Priority to semantic accuracy:* Terms related to life information must have semantic accuracy in translation. For example, “karaoke” can be translated as

“singing room”, “street food and drinks stand” and “bathhouse” and “guest house”, respectively. “Exemplary taxi” can be translated as "deluxe taxi".

2. Consideration of instructions for the translation of tourist places: If the term is used in the name of a tourist destination, it is recommended to follow the instructions for the translation of tourist places, taking into account the uniqueness of the geographical name and the communication skills between foreigners and local residents. For example, “Namdaemun Market” can be translated as “Namdamun Market”.

3. Romanization of elements and names: for thematic alleys, it is proposed to designate all elements by romanization in accordance with the instructions for translating artificial names of tourist places. For example, “Daegu Apjeong Alley” would be translated as “Daegu Traditional Medicine Street”. However, in the case of food lanes, all elements and food names should be romanized, and the back elements should be romanized.

4. Use of universal expressions: In the case of “alley”, it is suggested to use the expression “street” regardless of the nature and characteristics. This is due to research showing that "street" is a more universal expression than “ally”. Pure Korean included in the terminology should be designated by romanization to emphasize uniqueness.

5. Use of official English names: If a term has an official English name used by the competent authority or company concerned, it is recommended that this name be followed in preference. For example, “Kyobo Book Center” and “Noryangjin Fisheries Wholesale Market”.

These guidelines will help ensure that terms related to life information are translated accurately, taking into account the context and priority of reporting the facts.

Experience. In a study on the acceptability of translation of tourism terms from Korean into English in the context of experience, the main principles and examples are as follows:

1. Use of Romanization: All elements are expected to be written using Romanization. For example, the “Jeonju World Sound Festival” festival will be translated as “Jeonju International Traditional Music Festival”, and the “Traditional Time Zone Festival” festival will be translated as “Punky Traditional Timezone Festival”.

2. Consideration of characteristics: It is important to highlight the characteristics of the experience in translation. For example, the “Kochang Form Songzheng” Festival will be translated as “Gochang Moyang Fortress Festival” to convey the characteristics and back element of “Kochang”.

3. Use of appropriate instructions: When translating names containing natural or artificial place names, it is recommended to follow the appropriate translation instructions. For example, the “Songpanak Journey” festival can be translated as “Seongpanak Parasitic Cone Trail”.

4. Revealing uniqueness: In Korean, a language known to foreigners, the Roman letter is also used to emphasize uniqueness. For example, “Gwangju Kimchi Festival” would be translated as “Gwangju Kimchi Festival”.

5. Application of rules for the designation of cultural heritage: if the name of the festival or performance contains cultural values, the corresponding rules for designation of cultural heritage are used. For example, “Gangneung Danoe” would be translated as “Gangneung Danoe Festival”.

These principles and examples will help ensure acceptable translation of tourism terms, taking into account the context of the experience and the characteristics of the experience. The article presented the principles for standardizing the translation of tourist cultural terms in English, including names of travel destinations, lifestyle information and experiences. This made it possible to develop uniform recommendations for translation into English.

Conclusion: The development of guidelines for standardizing the translation of tourism terminology into English is crucial for promoting effective communication in the tourism industry. Collaborating with cultural property experts, reviewing drafts by native English speakers, and developing a system for studying theories of translation of cultural property are necessary steps to ensure accurate and adequate translation. Hiring competent translators and continuously improving their skills will enhance the process of translating cultural terms, leading to a better understanding of cultural information in English.

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